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Impact of Mobile Learning Approach on Secondary School Students' Achievement in Mathematics in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) on secondary school students' mathematics achievement in Owerri Municipal Council, Imo State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The quasi-experimental design, which employed a pre-test, post-test non-randomized control approach was adopted in the study. A sample of 254 SS2 students from two co-educational schools was purposively selected. Data were collected using a 30-item Algebra Achievement Test (AAT), with a reliability coefficient of 0.84. The experimental group was taught using MLA, while the control group received traditional "talk and chalk" instruction. Data analysis involved mean, standard deviation, and ANCOVA at a 0.05 significance level. Results showed a significant difference in achievement scores favoring MLA over traditional methods. However, no significant gender-based difference was found among students taught with MLA, indicating its effectiveness for both male and female learners. The study concludes that MLA enhances mathematics performance and recommends its adoption by secondary school teachers to improve student achievement.

Keywords: Mobile Learning Approach, Achievement, Mathematics.

INTRODUCTION

The success of any development-oriented society in the twenty-first century depends heavily on mathematics education. Mathematics provides useful, self-enhancing, and marketable skills. It provides fulfillment in employment and also offers learners an enriching way of seeing and understanding the world, an essential component for working as critical citizens in modern society (Ernest, 2009). Mathematics is the foundation of both science and technology, and it is so widely used in these domains that neither science nor technology nor business could exist without it (Nwoke, 2015). Mathematics works as a tool to understand many other subjects and languages. In a broad sense, it serves as the foundation for numerous fields, including astronomy, physics, engineering, and science. Mathematics is taught to motivate the learners, which allows for advancement in technology through science and technology (Gerdes in Jameela & Alib, 2016).

The importance of mathematics in a society led the Nigerian government to include it as a compulsory subject in the curriculum for both elementary and secondary school education. In fact, credit in mathematics at the secondary school level is a prerequisite to obtaining admission to study degree programs at any university in Nigeria. Sa'ad and Usman (2014) stated that in Nigeria, mathematics is given all the necessary importance in the curriculum and all policies related to education, right from primary to higher levels. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FGN) (2004), mathematics is one of the core subjects that pupils in primary and secondary school study. In addition, before being admitted to any postsecondary institution in Nigeria, students must pass mathematics as one of the required subjects at the credit level. The Comparative Education Study and Adaptation Centre (CESAC) (1982), cited in Sa'ad et al. (2014), reported that secondary school mathematics aims to achieve the following: 1) To enhance computational skills and foster the desire and ability to be accurate to a degree relevant to the problem at hand. 2. To develop precise, logical, and abstract thinking. 3. Improve problem-solving skills by applying mathematics knowledge. 4. To provide the necessary mathematical background for further education. 5. To stimulate and encourage creativity, originality, and curiosity in the learner.

Despite the attached importance to this singular subject, students' performance has continuously become a nightmare, as students are noted to perform poorly in both internal and external examinations. Jameela and Alib (2016) indicated that poor mathematical academic performance is also seen in secondary school students. Anaduaka and Okafor (2013) claim that students have continuously performed poorly in this crucial subject, particularly on external exams. Everyone finds it quite annoying when they struggle in mathematics in elementary and high school. Many students perceive mathematics as a challenging and dull subject, leading to emotions of inadequacy, hesitancy, and complexity. Suleiman and Hammed (2019) reported that WAEC results from 2009–2014 indicated that secondary school 'students' performance in core subjects (mathematics inclusive) is on the decline. Sa'ad et al. (2014) said that despite the fact that mathematics is given a lot of attention in Nigeria's educational system, it is depressing to see that in recent years, low performance has been reported in open exams. Even though FGN emphasizes the 60:40 ratio in favor of sciences for admission to higher institutions, low performance in mathematics is one of the main causes of the fall in science and technology courses and development.

The poor performance of students in mathematics at the secondary school level has been severely blamed on teachers' instructional approaches, lack of mathematical laboratories, lack of conducive learning environments, parental factors, peer group influence, career choice, students' attitudes, etc. John and Sincuba (2017) reported that the factors that cause poor performance in mathematics were found to be related to (a) teaching strategies; (b) content knowledge and understanding; (c) motivation and interest; (d) laboratory usage; and (e) syllabus non-compliance. Accordingly, Sa'ad et al. (2014) indicated that a number of factors contribute to senior high school students' poor performance in mathematics, including underqualified teachers, instructional materials, libraries, laboratories, students' negative attitudes, inappropriate teaching methods, anxiety, home backgrounds, crowded classrooms, interrupted instruction, dyscalculia, teachers who lack motivation, and others. Ibrahim et al. (2024) indicated that poor performance in mathematics in Nigeria arises from negative student 'attitudes, ineffective curricula, and inadequately trained teachers. They laid emphasis on curriculum revision, improved teaching strategies, and the integration of technology to enhance student engagement and achievement. Akaazua et al. (2017) concluded that a student's positive attitude toward a subject, as well as the teacher's technique of instruction, promoted meaningful learning and, as a result, idea development. It is therefore pertinent to search for ways of encouraging a positive attitude in learners towards learning in order to improve the learning outcome in mathematics. While offering ways for raising students' mathematics performance, Ojimba (2012) mentioned the use of educational games and aids, as well as computer-aided instruction, as tactics for raising students' mathematics performance. With a focus on mobile technology for learning. Incorporating technology into the teaching and learning process can help learners do better in mathematics.

One of the main concerns in the academic community has been the persistently low secondary school mathematics achievement of students as a result of the inefficient traditional mathematics classroom. Traditional methods of teaching mathematics, which involve teacher-centered instruction, rote memorization, and limited student 'engagement, are no longer adequate in addressing the students' learning needs in the 21st century. In order to resolve these problems, poor-performing mathematics

teachers in classes nowadays are using a range of technological tools, with varying degrees of effectiveness (Souter, n.d.).

The National Council of Teachers of Mathematics encouraged the use of technology in the mathematics classroom, and this has increased technology-enhanced classrooms in many developed nations of the world. Amoo (2010) argues that if junior and senior secondary schools integrate high-quality ICT resources that students can access and utilize, there is optimism that students' attitudes will change; there may be increased motivation to master school topics (including mathematics). This is also determined by how effectively mathematics teachers use ICT resources in the classroom to assist students. With the increased level of availability of mobile technologies and access to smartphones and the internet, mobile learning has emerged as a reliable instructional strategy. Mobile learning provides students with flexibility, accessibility, interactivity, and multimedia tools that can help them understand, solve problems, and achieve in mathematics. It is widely acknowledged that mobile learning technology significantly improves mathematics education and learning. According to Dahiru and Biya (2010), employing mobile devices for mathematics instruction has various benefits. These include providing students with tools that assist collaboration and learning, such as text and voice chat, instant messaging, and multimedia presentations of mathematical topics. According to the study, preparatory students took their mathematics courses utilizing mobile technology equipment. In a research, Matthew and Damian (2013) reported that pre-service math teachers' usage of mobile learning enhanced their ability to teach mathematics by fostering debates, idea sharing, information storage, and informal information retrieval. Gupta (2012), in a study on the use of mobile technology in mathematics education, discovered that, in contrast to a typical traditional learning environment, students found it easier to interpret graphs and acquire new, unknown mathematical ideas.

VaniKalloo and Permanand (2012) employed game-based learning, personalization, and different learning methodologies in combination with mobile learning to assist students in improving their performance in mathematics. Zameni and Kardan (2011), in a study, concluded that utilization of the information and communications technology is effective in changing the attitude and stability of subject matters, reasoning and creativity, and finally active learning of mathematics. Kay and Knaack (2008) and Li and Ma (2010) noted that using computer technology and learning objects, respectively, does improve mathematical achievement if other factors are also considered. Demir and Akpinar (2018) revealed that as compared to traditional learning, mobile learning significantly enhances academic achievement. Hwang and Chang (2011) indicate that m-learning not only catches students' interaction but also increases their success. Ozan (2013) has discovered that students' performance is positively impacted by mobile devices. When utilized appropriately, technology can improve the caliber of mathematics instruction. When technology is integrated in the classroom, it may help to produce learners who can reason logically when solving problems (Stolts, 2012). Additionally, learner performance improves in mathematics when technology is utilized for higher-order learning. Collaborative learning facilitated by technology improves students' performance on activities that require problem solving (Stolts, 2012). It is thought that students' success or achievement is greatly increased when technology is employed in the classroom in an acceptable manner. Additionally, technology-mediated learning encourages cooperation, teamwork, and active learning among students and helps teachers give students quick feedback. It also allows teachers to provide their students with flexibility and personalized learning experiences.

Gender is one factor that has been instrumental to students' achievement in mathematics at secondary school levels. Chebet (2016) declared that the topic of gender disparities in secondary mathematics has received a lot of attention from studies, with the observed disparities in mathematics achievement between boys and girls being controversial. Asante (2010) noted that while scientists seek to address the underrepresentation of women in mathematics, physical sciences, and engineering at the highest levels, gender discrepancies in mathematical achievement and aptitude have remained a subject of concern. Mbutia, cited in Chebet (2016), discovered that in mixed-sex secondary schools, female students outperformed their male counterparts, but in single-sex secondary schools, male students outperformed their female counterparts. The use of instructional methodologies that do not provide equal learning chances to both male and female students result in disparities in their mathematics achievement. Boaler, cited in Ajai and Imoko (2015), is of the view that the different learning goals of girls and boys leave girls at a disadvantage in competitive environments. Despite their diverse ways of thinking, both boys and girls preferred a mathematics program that allowed them to work at their own

pace. Since comprehension is the goal, girls appreciate experiences that let them reflect and formulate their own thoughts. Conversely, boys place greater emphasis on precision and speed, viewing them as markers of success. Boys can learn mathematics in a competitive environment with textbooks and still score well. When females are treated differently than boys when it comes to using technology and being encouraged to utilize it, gender equity issues arise. Better performance is ensured when male and female students use mobile learning technologies to see themselves as equals who can compete and work together in the classroom.

Irrespective of the contributions of mobile learning approaches in secondary school students' mathematics outcomes, there exists limited empirical evidence on its effectiveness in secondary school mathematics teaching and learning in the Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State. Considering the challenges such as student engagement, teacher readiness, and limited infrastructures that may retard the successful implementation of mobile learning in mathematics, it's also not clear whether the integration of mobile technologies will have a substantial impact on student achievement when compared to traditional teaching techniques.

Therefore, this study was carried out to investigate the effect of the mobile learning approach (MLA) on secondary school students' achievement in mathematics in the Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the impact of the mobile learning approach (MLA) on students' achievement and attitude in mathematics. Specifically, the study will determine whether:

- 1). Students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) will have better achievement than those taught using the traditional "talk and chalk" approach.
- 2). The achievement of students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) will be dependent on gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1) What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) and those taught using the traditional "talk and chalk" approach?
- 2) What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA)?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) and those taught using the traditional "talk and chalk" approach.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the quasi-experimental design of the pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control type. The design was used to assess the influence of the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) on students' mathematical achievement. The study's population consists of all 3,266 senior secondary 11 (SS2) students from the nine government-owned secondary schools in Imo State's Owerri Municipal Council. Four co-educational secondary schools were purposefully chosen for the study based on location and gender composition. In each of the chosen schools, two intact classes were randomly assigned to the experiment and control groups. This was done since it was not possible for the researchers to embark on randomization of the samples needed for the study due to the school program. The study's sample size is two hundred and fifty-four (254) students from the intact courses used for the study. This includes one hundred and fifteen (115) men and one hundred and thirty-nine (139) women. The experiment group has 130 pupils (70 males and 60 females), while the control group has 124 students (45 males and 79 females).

The data required for the study will be generated using a researcher-made 30-item objective test question titled "**Algebra Achievement Test (AAT)**." The construction of the test instrument was guided by a table of specifications based on the topics the students were taught. The instrument has

four alternatives (A-D), one correct response, and three detractors. Two mathematics education professionals and a measurement and evaluation specialist assessed the instrument's validity. They determined if the test instrument was appropriate for measuring the study's objectives. The instruments were restructured where necessary based on their reports. To determine the reliability of the instrument, copies of the instrument were administered to 30 students outside the study sample in another school with the same characteristics. This was accomplished within two weeks utilizing the test-retest approach, and the test instrument's reliability was assessed to be 0.84 using Pearson's Product Moment correlation, which was appropriate for the study. To administer the instrument, a pretest was given to both the control and experiment groups to assess their cognitive readiness. Then, the experiment group was taught algebra topics—simultaneous equations and quadratic equations—using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) by a research assistant trained on the approach with the aid of the researchers. The research assistants were taught for three weeks at one hour per contact, three days a week. To teach the experiment group, the researchers created a detailed lesson plan explaining the step-by-step implementation of the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) in teaching algebra. First, the students were taught the topics using a detailed lesson plan by the research assistant, after which the software that was used for the study was downloaded and installed on the mobile gadgets, such as branded iPads, phones, etc., for the selected students. Then the students were guided through using the mobile gadgets to learn and solve problems associated with simultaneous linear and quadratic equations as the process was also projected on the screen. Students were permitted to learn individually and in groups, communicating with one another via mobile technologies, and they were allowed to ask questions and interact with the researcher and research assistant as needed. The researchers observed the entire process to ensure that it was carried out as planned; students were also permitted to study outside of the classroom throughout the treatment period using a mobile device, which was monitored by the researchers. The control groups were taught the identical topics by their usual classroom teachers concurrently using the traditional "talk and chalk" approach as indicated on the lesson plan. The approach was teacher-centered, which placed the lesson control on the teacher alone. The process lasted for ten weeks, after which a post-test was administered to both groups using a rearranged format of the pre-test instrument and marked over 100 percent. The generated data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) and those taught using the traditional “talk and chalk” approach?*

Table 1: summary of students’ scores in experiment and control groups

Group	N	Test	Mean	SD	Mean diff	Achievement diff
Experiment	130	Post-test	54.02	11.08	21.32	18.51
		Pre-test	32.70	9.22		
Control	124	Post-test	35.82	9.66	2.81	
		Pre-test	33.01	9.41		

Table 1 shows that the experiment group had a pre-test mean of 32.70 and a standard deviation of 9.22; they had a post-test mean of 54.02 and a standard deviation of 11.08. These resulted in a mean difference of 21.32 in the experiment group. Also, the control group had a pre-test mean of 33.01 and a standard deviation of 9.41, with a post-test mean of 35.82 and a standard deviation of 9.66. These resulted in a mean difference of 2.81 in the control group. The results collectively gave an achievement difference of 18.51 in favor of the experiment group.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA)?*

Table 2: Summary of gender achievements in experiment group

Gender	N	Test	Mean	SD	Mean diff	Achievement diff
Male	70	Post-test	54.32	11.08	20.67	0.62
		Pre-test	33.65	9.35		
Female	60	Post-test	54.30	11.13	21.29	
		Pre-test	33.01	9.31		

Table 2 shows that male students in the experiment group had a pre-test mean of 33.65 and a standard deviation of 9.35; they had a post-test mean of 54.32 and a standard deviation of 11.08. These resulted in a mean difference of 20.67. Also, female students had a pre-test mean of 33.01 and a standard deviation of 9.31, with a post-test mean of 54.30 and a standard deviation of 11.13. These resulted in a mean difference of 21.29. The results collectively gave an achievement difference of 0.62 in favor of male students.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) and those taught using the traditional “talk and chalk” approach.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA analysis on students’ scores in experiment and control groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	21903.963 ^a	4	5475.991	51.610	.000
Intercept	28621.975	1	28621.975	269.758	.000
Covariate	115.166	1	115.166	1.085	.298
Method	21690.530	1	21690.530	204.430	.000
Gender	329.168	1	329.168	3.102	.079
Method * Gender	525.512	1	525.512	4.953	.027
Error	26419.486	249	106.102		
Total	565738.000	254			
Corrected Total	48323.449	253			

Table 3 shows that $F(1, 249) = 204.530, P = 0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted. This implies that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) and those taught using the traditional approach.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA).

Table 3 shows that $F(1, 249) = .079, P = 3.102 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis is upheld and the alternative rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion will be based on the results evident from the study.

The study found that applying a mobile learning approach (MLA) considerably improved students’ mathematical ability. Those in the experimental group taught mathematics using MLA had an average mean achievement higher than those taught using the “talk and chalk” method. Further statistical analysis revealed a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using the Mobile Learning Approach (MLA) and those taught using the traditional “talk and chalk” approach. This result is suspected to be due to the dynamic and engaging nature of the approach, which enhanced students understanding and achievement in the subject. Students had the chance to access lessons and other materials outside of the classroom setting. The approach enhanced self-paced learning, allowing students to revisit learned materials and practice problem-solving at their own pace, giving room to individual learning styles and needs. Students had room for collaborative learning, instant feedback, and development of critical thinking skills. The result is in agreement with Wang et al. (2021), which indicated that students in the mobile learning system (MLS) group showed significantly better improvement in mathematics learning achievement than those in the typical instruction (TI) group, particularly in comprehension and application levels, indicating a positive impact of mobile learning on students’ achievement. It also aligns with Chau et al.’s (2022) research, which revealed that utilizing the mobile software considerably improved students’ average assessment test results compared to screening tests, demonstrating that mobile learning positively influences students’ achievement in mathematics by enhancing autonomous learning and motivation.

The study also revealed that the mobile learning approach (MLA) enhanced students' achievement in mathematics irrespective of gender. Male and female pupils in the experiment group performed equally well in mathematics. The study also found no significant difference in mean achievement scores between male and female mathematics students taught using the mobile learning approach (MLA). This result could be attributed to the fact that the mobile learning approach (MLA) encouraged peer interaction and cooperative learning, which does not give room for gender stereotypes and supports every learner in the mathematics classroom. It also enhanced students' confidence and reduced anxiety. This result is consistent with Fabian et al. (2016), which showed a small effect favoring male students in enjoyment of mathematics and confidence with technology at earlier tests, but the effects diminished at the post-test levels, indicating no significant differences in gender achievements. It further aligns with Salami and Spangenberg (2024), which indicated that ICT facilities significantly improved mathematics achievement among secondary school students and reduced the gender gap in performance. Emphasizing the necessity of incorporating technology into instruction to help students improve their mathematics abilities and understanding.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings show that the Mobile Learning strategy (MLA) is a more effective means of teaching mathematics in secondary schools than the standard "talk-and-chalk" method, as it considerably improved students' achievement. MLA's effectiveness is not gender-based, as both male and female students increased their performance and expressed equally positive perceptions of the technique. These results indicate that the mobile learning approach is not only an inclusive method but also a meaningful and impactful tool for enhancing mathematics learning among secondary school students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Mathematics teachers at the secondary school level should adopt the mobile learning approach (MLA) in teaching to enhance students learning outcomes.
2. Mathematics teachers should engage in professional development through workshops, conferences, and symposiums to gain the skills of integrating mobile learning (MLA) in mathematics classrooms.
3. Education stakeholders and managers should allocate resources to schools to ensure that both students and teachers have access to reliable mobile devices, internet connectivity and dependable power supply.

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